

General Problems of Sciences

Leo G. Sapogin¹✍️, V. A. Dzhanibekov², Yu. A. Ryabov³

¹Department of Physics, Technical University (MADI), 64 Leningradsky pr., A-319, Moscow, 125319, Russia

²Department of Cosmophysics, Tomsk State University, 36 Lenina st., 634050, Tomsk, Russia.

³Department of Mathematics, Technical University (MADI), 64 Leningradsky pr., A-319, 125319, Moscow, Russia

Abstract: The present article discusses the problems of new Unitary Quantum Theory in its applications to the different aspects of the reality. There are spectacular examples of such applications.

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Introduction

It seems that the majority of researches have absolutely forgotten the fact that one of the master spirits of contemporary world, A. Einstein, till the end of his life had not adopted the standard quantum mechanics at all. Better to cite his well-known words: «Great initial success of the quantum theory could not make me believe in a dice game being the basis of it. I do not believe this principal conception being an appropriate foundation for physics as a whole... Physicists think me an old fool, but I am convinced that the future development of physics will go in another direction than heretofore I reject the main idea of modern statistical quantum theory... I'm quite sure that the existing statistical character of modern quantum theory should be ascribed to the fact that that theory operates with incomplete descriptions of physical systems only.» A.Einstein (back translation).

At the first stage of quantum mechanics evolution in the frame of classical physics theory the mechanism of corpuscular-wave dualism was not discovered at all, as it was done later in the UQT [2-4, 13-15, 23]. It is worth a surprise that the super abstract quantum ideology *ad hoc* designed by Niels Bohr was suitable in general for the description of quantum reality. An explorer did contradict anything by strictly using new frequently paradoxical quantum rules, and any paradox could be removed by the simple prohibition of its analysis. Although many researches tried to solve these problems they were not successful. The outspoken interpretation of quantum theory had become out of any criticism. More over the determination of simulators describing one of the sides of quantum reality had been announced as the main target of quantum science, while the picture in figures and_a-going_had become simply an optional target.

Nevertheless one general philosophic problem had been remaining: the dual principles of the fundamental physics. There were particles as some points being the source of a field that could not be reduced to the field itself; the researchers did not do their utmost, though. Introduction of this micro-particle had resulted in a wide range of different divergences - anybody knows that electric power of a point charge equals infinity. A lot of ideas had appeared, absolutely brilliant ideas from mathematical point of view, suitable for these appearing infinities abolishing. We can use as a cover the words of P.A.Dirac: “most physicists are completely satisfied with the existing situation. They consider relativistic quantum field theory and electrodynamics to be quite perfect theories and it is not necessary to be anxious about the situation. I should say that I do not like that at all, because according to such perfect theory we have to neglect, without any reason, infinities that appear in the equations. It is just mathematical nonsense. Usually in mathematics the value can be rejected only in the case it were too small, but not because it is infinitely big and someone would like to get rid of it”. Direction in Physics, New York, 1978 (back translation).

The substantial success of the quantum mechanics (particularly in the stationary cases) was based on the simple correlation of de Broglie wave length and geometric properties of potential. Formally the particle was considered as a point; in other case it was difficult to add probability amplitude character to the wave function. But the point-character of a charge as well the principle of Complementarity did not allow to go ahead in the elementary particles structure and thus the further development of the quantum theory of the field in the frames of the assumed paradigm had resulted in total fiasco of the field quantum theory itself.

Leo G. Sapogin (Correspondence)

sapogin@cnf.madi.ru

+7-499-1550390

There is another concept in physics; it comes from W.Clifford, A.Einstein, E.Schrodinger and Louis de Broglie in which the particle is considered as a bunch (wave packet) of a certain unified field. The position of associates of the concept would be expressed the most clearly by the following words of A.Einstein: *“We could therefore regard matter as being constituted by the regions of space in which the field is extremely strong. A thrown stone is, from this point of view, a changing field in which the states of the greatest field intensity travel through space with the velocity of the stone. There is no place in this new kind of physics both for the field and the matter, for the Field is the only reality... and the laws of motion would automatically follow from the laws of field”*. (back translation). By (M. Jemmer, [1]) definition of the particle as a wave packet is the item for some unitary theory.

The first articles concerning this matter were published in [2-4]. The entire term “unitary” belongs to who has classified quantum wave’s theories, and it is correlated with the theories that represent particle as a wave packet. In Unitary Quantum Theory a particle is described as a wave packet that in its movement is periodically spreading along the Metagalaxy and is gathering again. For such moving wave packet both the relativistic and the classical mechanics follow from these unitary quantum equations, probably the Maxwell equations and the gravitation follow from exact UQT equations [8,13-15], but this has not been proved yet being the problem of the future. Nevertheless the UQT scalar equation (a telegraph type) in general makes it possible to obtain not only Schrodinger but also Maxwell equations [14, 15].

The field of investigations of the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory (UUQT) is the most profound level of substance: the level of elementary particles and quantum effects.

As well known all particles have besides corpuscular properties wave properties too (particles can interfere with each other or with themselves), and their

behavior is described by means of the wave function. In the case of a particle moved in the free space, the wave function is described as de Broglie plane wave which wavelength is inverse to the momentum of the particle. If the particle is slowing down or accelerating by applied fields then its wavelength is increasing or decreasing, respectively. The wave itself has no physical interpretation, but the squared value of its amplitude is proportional to the probability to find the particle in a defined place. That is why these waves are also called “waves of probability” or “waves of knowledge”, etc.

There is another problem: the particle has no exact value for coordinate and for momentum at the same time, although either value could be measured arbitrarily closely (uncertainty relation). That is why the definition of trajectory of a quantum particle has no sense.

As opposed to the laws of the classical physics with its determinism where one can predict results of the motion of separate particles, in the quantum theory one can only predict the probability of the behavior of separate particles. Even the nature does not know the way a particle goes by in the case of diffraction by two slits. But it is not the most depressing. The Quantum Physics has wave-corpuscle dualism as well as field dualism and matter dualism. All particles act as sources of field, but it appears that they are only points which have no relation to these fields, and one can’t tell anything in concrete about them.

Let us continue to confuse the reader. We shall consider an extremely simple experiment with single particles in the terms of the modern quantum theory. It will allow us to understand what is going on and will be useful for us in the future.

Let single photons fall on a semitransparent mirror directed at the angle of 45 degrees to their stream. Semitransparents means that a half of the falling light is reflected and another one passes by. Photon counters are installed on the paths of reflected and passed rays (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Experiments with individual photons on semitransparent mirror.

In the terms of the wave theory everything is simple: an incident wave will be reflected and will be passed partially.

But particles as they are indivisible have to be reflected or be passed by. If a counter of reflected beam's particles registers an event it is evidently to suppose that the second counter will register nothing. It is easy to see that if one will re-unite passed and reflected beams and sends them to the screen then...it's all about the way how we are going to argue.

From the wave theory there will be an interference pattern, but from the corpuscular theory it will not occur. In fact, an interference pattern is observed in experiments even for single photons, and our suppositions are wrong to say the least. **In order to spare the doubts about how is it possible, it is better to forbid one to think about it.** And the principle of Complementarity in modern physics does it in any case.

It allows to ask only the questions for which it's possible to give an answer by experimentally only. When one tries to find a particle it means that one rejects to observe the interference pattern and vice versa. As though we could know from experiment either a particle has passed by or has been reflected, we would realize the real particle behavior. But it's impossible to do by the means of macro-instruments.

The principle of Complementarity makes the quantum physics descriptively inaccessible. *There are many experiments, that we just cannot explain without considering the wave function as a wave that influences on the whole region and not as particles appearing may be here, may be there, as it is possible in the terms of the clearly probabilistic point*

of view"(E.Schrodinger). In other words a wave acts in the whole area simultaneously, not "may be here, may be there", otherwise there wouldn't be any diffraction or interference.

Eventually we have to admit that the prohibitions of the principle of Complementarity respond to the weakness philosophy, and the role of this principle is obviously analogous to the role of a calorie, a phlogiston and other obsolete concepts.

Unified field theory approach.

Let us ask the questions that are forbidden by the principle of Complementarity. What is the wave of an electron? What is the behavior of an electron indeed, when nobody looks at it? (it's natural behavior?) How does it manage to go through a potential barrier when its energy is less than the barrier height (tunneling effect)? How does it, as it is indivisible, go simultaneously by two slits which are divided by a great distance in comparison with its own size? What kind of structure has an atom of hydrogen constructed at the lowest energy state (*s*-state)? How can the probabilistic consideration of a wave function to result from the mathematical formalism of the theory? Why is the actual Quantum Mechanics reversible? This is a primary law, and the irreversibility has to follow from it for dispose the paradoxes in the statistical mechanics. Last but not least: what structure has the electron itself described in the terms of probability? This is a huge complex of mysteries. All (or almost all) physicists resigned and even prefer not to speak about it. But there is also someone who does speak. Paul Langevin even called the formalism of Quantum Mechanics with its principle of Complementarity the "intellectual debauch".

E. Schrodinger wrote that he "was happy for three months" when he had got the idea to consider the

particle as the packet (bunch) of de Broglie waves until the English mathematician Darwin proved that the packet would spread and vanish. But the trouble of all of these attempts (E.Schrodinger, Louis de Broglie, etc) was the fact they always tried to construct it by means of de Broglie waves with such dispersion that any wave packet has to spread. The including of nonlinearity (Louis de Broglie) just extremely complicated the problem but didn't solve it.

Unified Unitary Quantum Theory Interpretation.

The critical feature of the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory (UUQT) is the fact that it describes the particle as a bunch (packet) of certain unified field, but not as a questionable structure of the de Broglie waves of probability.

For spying upon the particles which we consider as very small bunches of the real field, let us consider a Hypothetic Observer (HO) which is able to measure the parameters of these bunches with the hypothetic microprobe. Dimensions of microprobe are much less than the dimensions of the particles. The result of

these measurements will be certain structure function that describes bunch of the real field. Obviously, this hypothetic HO and microprobe couldn't exist, but our thought experiments will be as simple as possible.

If we choose the dispersion of these partial waves equal to linear, we could have an extremely curious process, which mathematical formulation used never before. If we have dispersion, then harmonic components of partial waves propagated with different velocities will result in spreading of the wave packet over all space or over all Metagalaxy. Mathematical investigations show that the spreading goes on without any changes of the form of the wave packet; but at the end, there is a moment when a wave packet vanishes at all. Where does its energy disappear to? It remains in the form of harmonic components that set up a certain background in any point in the space. As these waves are not damped and continue to propagate with velocity of their own, then after a while the wave packet begins to revive in another point, but its sign will be changed at that. During the motion, the packet will appear and disappear periodically (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Behaviour of wave packet in linear dispersion medium (i.e., rather like a series of stroboscopic photographs).

The envelope of this process is locus of points, locus of points of its maximum, it is a sinusoidal quantity and it rests in all reference frames; in other words, its phase velocity is equal zero in any reference frame, i.e. it's relativistically invariant (only by means of it the results of the relativistic dynamics are absolutely correct). If we change a reference frame, we will receive a different value of wavelength of the envelope, but it will be motionless as well. As the computing shows the wavelength of the envelope is exactly equal to de Broglie wavelength, and the dependence of this wavelength on packet velocity is the same! As you see, all the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory is occupied with the resolute exploiting of this basic idea. It should be stressed that this periodical appearing and disappearing of

particles doesn't refer to the Quantum Mechanics, as an immovable packet doesn't oscillate. The requirement of the relativistic invariance, that would be the main requirement for any theory, specifies the idea further. It states the following: when Lord has excited in space continuum wave packet with his finger and then he has taken it away, then the packet will go on oscillating as a membrane or a string after impact. The frequency ω_S of these free oscillations is very high: it is proportional to the rest energy of the particle and it is equal to the frequency of the so called Schrodinger's trembling ("zitterbewegung").

$$\omega_S = \frac{mc^2}{\hbar\gamma}, \quad \gamma = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$
 Within the motion there arise de Broglie vibrations with frequency $\omega_B = mv^2 / \hbar\gamma$ due to

dispersion. At small energies $\omega_S \gg \omega_B$ and the presence of quick own oscillations has no influence on experiment. So, all quantum phenomena result from de Broglie oscillations.

Figure 3.

The value of frequency ω_B tends to ω_S with growth of energy and resonance phenomenon appears that results in oscillating amplitude increase and in mass growth. Thus the well-known graph of particle mass dependence on the velocity (Fig.3) approaching to light s velocity constitutes actually a half of usual resonance curve for forced oscillation of harmonic oscillator if energy dissipation is absent. In the case when $v \rightarrow c$, frequency $\omega_B \rightarrow \omega_S$ (frequency resonance), $\gamma \rightarrow 0$ and the beats appear with difference frequency

$$\omega_d = \omega_s - \omega_B \approx mc^2\gamma / \hbar$$
 and particle will obtain absolutely new low-frequency envelop with wave length

$$\Lambda = \frac{h}{mc\gamma}$$

This is a new wave. This can be checked experimental in CERN. In ultra-relativistic limit case the value of Λ becomes much greater as typical dimension of quantum system it (new wave) interacts with. Now the length of new wave grows with energy contrary to de Broglie wave length slowly decreasing, and particle requires the form of quasi-stationary

wave packet moving in accordance with classical laws. That explains the success of hydrodynamics fluid theory concerning with numerous particle birth when the packet having extremely big amplitude is able to split into series of packets with smaller amplitudes. But such splitting processes characterize not only high-energy particles. Something like this takes place at small energies also, but overwhelming majority of arising wave packets are under the barrier and so will not be detected. It would be perfect to examine by experiments at future accelerators the appearance of such new wave with the length growing together with energy [2-4, 17-19].

If our HO places at the way of motion of the wave packet quite a number of his microprobes, then due to the dispersion spreading and rebuilding he can observe the envelope of this process, and all of this will not be at variance to the general Quantum Mechanics, as this envelope corresponds to the wave function. This figure, i.e. a sinusoidal envelope with a regular shape, can be seen by the HO in the only case: if the only single particle would exist in the world. But the real world consists of an enormous number of particles moving each other with different velocities. The partial waves (harmonic components) of those particles which have vanished at this moment can be summarized and emerge real fluctuations of the field or in other words the vacuum

fluctuations that will act in a random manner. These fluctuations could destroy all idyllic character of measurements of our HO (Hypothetic Observer) for single particle in Universe because the sinusoidal envelope will be distorted by vacuum fluctuations and it will be difficult to separate it clearly.

Any wave packet that is described in the terms of the becoming structural function could be decomposed by means of Fourier transforming into plane sinusoidal (partial) waves. These waves are infinitely numerous, and their amplitude is infinitesimal. If we summarize them it will emerge zero everywhere except of the area occupied by the structure function. Thus the structure function could be represented either as a function of time (time representation) or as a function of an amplitude of harmonic components related to frequency (spectral representation). It is absolutely equivalent to mathematical representations. Now there is no necessity in the principle Complementary that was a very convenient view *ad hoc*.

It is easy and clear how the synthesis of corpuscular and wave properties is realized. Corpuscular properties occur due to the localization of a wave packet in a small spatial region. The wave properties of the de Broglie waves can be explained in the following way: when the wave packet approaches to the diffraction system (for example Young's experiment with two slits) then we have an ordinary diffraction of partial waves by splites, and the diffraction pattern of partial waves appears at the screen. HO could observe it with his microprobes.

As these packets are not overlapped then everything is linear and the superposition of the partial waves creates a total diffraction pattern modulated by the de Broglie wave, although the plain de Broglie wave doesn't exist at all. It should be stressed that de Broglie wave is a packets locus of points of

maximum in his motion, and it is a superposition of partial waves, that is why it appears in any diffraction and interference experiment.

Quantum measurements

Let us try to consider real instruments, which are always macroscopic. Atomic nuclei and electron shells are situated very near to each other and form a very numerous, but discrete series. A transition from the one such a state to another is a quantum jump. **That is why the absorption and emitting of energy between the atomic systems is carried out by means of the quanta.** However, it doesn't mean that in the motion process the quantum or the particle propagates as something constant and indivisible. The energy of the particle can be divided or changed by vacuum fluctuations. The wave packet of a photon, for example, can, in the issue of the overlapping of vacuum fluctuation, turn into meson at short time, and photon can disguise oneself as a proton or as a neutron. It s assumed in the ordinary quantum field theory that a proton has an atmosphere mesons; it follows from the interpretation of the results of its collisions with another particles. There is no mesons atmosphere indeed. A proton appears and disappears during its motion constantly at the de Broglie wavelength, and its mass changes periodically from the double value of a proton's mass to zero, taken on the intermediate values of mesons masses.

Eventually, all of the quantum measurements are based on energy absorption and present inconvertible processes [5, 6, 13-15]. For every instrument founded a particle will operate, a quantum of energy is needed at least, thus it is a threshold energy of instrument defining it's responsively. By the way, we would like to notice that our HO (Hypothetic Observer) uses the instruments with zero threshold energy that is why it can register even vacuum fluctuations.

Fig.4.

Let us consider the process of interaction of a particle with a macro-instrument [5, 6]. As soon as the particle is a wave packet, its energy is proportional to

the intensity of the packet, but it can be changed because of periodic spreading's and appearances. Besides the packet itself can be divided during the

interactions. *The macro-instrument to register a particle has to wait for a moment when the total energy of the particle and of the fluctuation of the atom would be more or equal to threshold energy.* It is clear that the probability of the operation of the apparatus will be proportional to the amplitude of the wave packet, or more exactly, to the value of intensity of the envelope of the wave function. If the wave packet with a too low intensity in comparison with threshold energy of the macro-instrument approaches to the macro-instrument, the great fluctuation of vacuum is required, but the probability of such an event is too small, and it means that the probability to detect the particle is small too (Fig. 4). The theory of the quantum measurements is developed in the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory (UUQT), and the statistical interpretation follows now from the theory, but not just postulated, as it was before in the conventional quantum theory. ***This point of view requires automatically that the value of the dispersion of vacuum fluctuations is finite that, in another turn, requires the finiteness of the Universe.***

Unitary quantum illustrations.

The uncertainty relation arises because energy and momentum are not constants, but they periodically change because of the dispersion owing to disappearance and appearance of the particle [2-4]. Besides because of statistical laws of measurements with macroinstruments, there is no any way to measure anything accurately owing to the unpredictable fluctuations of the vacuum. HO (Hypothetic Observer) could predict the coordinate, the momentum or the energy of the packet, if he would be the only one in the Universe, i.e. in the case of absence of the vacuum fluctuations.

The presence of unpredictable vacuum fluctuations makes all of the laws of the micro-world principally statistical for any observer. An accurate prediction of expected events requires an accurate knowledge of the vacuum fluctuation in any moment of time, what is impossible, because it is necessary to have the information on the structure and the behavior of any packet (particle) in the universe and to control their motion. The mechanical determinism of Laplace went absolutely lost in the modern physics as well as in the future one. Maxwell was right when he told; *“the true logic of the universe is calculation of the probabilities”*. (back translation).

The envelope of partial waves, occurring due to linear transformations at the wave packet and being in the ruins of splitting of the packet corresponds to Huygens principle. It explains how the relating of a moving particle with a monochromatic de Broglie wave is formally possible, propagating in the

direction of the motion, and with all wave properties. There are partial waves that we consider as participants of diffraction and interference, but due to the principle of superposition we get the same result as if it a de Broglie wave would participate at the process.

The new linear equations of the UUQT allow the time inversion with simultaneous replacing of the wave function with a conjugated one, with the formal reversibility. Actually this reversibility takes place just in the case if the Universe consisted of the only one particle, as in the real world the recovering of the previous vacuum fluctuation is also needed for the total reversibility of the process. But there is a simultaneous reversibility of all processes in the Universe required for it that is impossible. It doesn't mean that quantum processes are inconvertible, just the reversibility has a statistical character, but **now direction of the current of time defines entropy only.**

The envelope, introduced before, is accurately monochromatic, but it does not exist as a traveling plane wave with such properties in the reality. Though it is related to the energy of the particle, the following definitions, such as “waves of the probability”, “waves of the knowledge”, could be related with it too. In contrast to the general quantum theory, now a very important phase is coming. It is the most easy to show it as the tunneling effect.

We would like to mention these established quantum phenomena to the reader. If we have a sufficiently narrow barrier with the height that is larger than the energy of an incident particle, according to the classical mechanics it will never go through the barrier. In the general quantum theory, the incident wave reflects and passes by partially, and we have a finite quantity of the probability that the particle will be behind the barrier. In these cases the general Quantum Mechanics states that the particle makes a tunnel in the barrier for itself, hiding the method of creation of this tunnel.

Let us listen to what HO says of this process? If a particle is approaching closely to a potential barrier in the phase of an absolute collapse, then it easily goes through the barrier, not interacting with it because of linear of all of equations for the small amplitude of the field. It just appears behind the barrier, without interacting with it, if its width is much less than de Broglie wavelength. And there is no necessity for it to make a tunnel. However, if it approaches in the phase with the maximal value of the packet, then the particle would be reflected because of the nonlinear interaction of the waves with the field of the barrier.

Now let us return to the experiment with the semitransparent mirror, discussed above. In terms of the described point of view, the wave packet (particle) will be divided at the mirror and enter in every beam, that depends on the packet phase near the mirror and on the structure of the mirror in this place. We have, in general, two not equal wave packets fragments with less values of the amplitude that can interfere. The changing of the parts of the fragments does not follow by because all process are linear, i.e. they are not dependants on amplitude. Besides the probability of detecting of the fragments is reduced, because an appreciable fluctuation of the vacuum is necessary for arising of threshold of detection of the counter. Consequently, in the results of the measurements the particles have to be lost or be observed as single particles in both of the beams simultaneously. The creation of two particles from a single is not a confusing fact, because the energy of the fragments will be reconstructed to the necessary level by means of the vacuum fluctuation. Note, the statement of Standard Quantum Mechanics that the particle may be presented simultaneously in many points of quantum world sounds strange from the common sense and remained for decades without any understanding of principal things. Within bounds of UQT scientific explanations are correct in principle.

At present time we have an ambiguous situation when high-tech experiments with fantastic results have been carried out, for example the classical experiments of Brown and Twiss and the variations of them (Fig. 1). It was found out that frequently both of the counters detect particles simultaneously, that is confirmed by the proposed mechanism. Furthermore, most of such experiments (including experiments with entangled photons) confirm directly this interpretation. The results of experiments with entangled particles are quite simple and understandable within bounds of UQT, and the idea to seek some over light mystic relations between particles is fully meaningless.

In consequence, an increasing number of photon pairs is always observed in the beam of light. However, it was found out that it is possible to carry out experiments whose effect remains also in the situation when there is no any way for any induced radiation. If we will collide particles of any kind, and if in the colliding point one or two particles are vanished, then they have to go against another without any interaction. Indeed, in the proton-proton interactions 6% of the particles don't interact, but go through the others. An analogous effect takes place in the atom of hydrogen in the state of minimum of energy. It is well known that this s -state is not rotational, and Bohr-Sommerfeld's atom model describes the spectrum strictly in the relativistic case.

If we apply this model to the s -state of the electron, we will obtain that the paths of the electron pass through the nuclear, and they were early excepted as absolutely absurd. Today it is clear that an electron just oscillates along a straight, going through the proton. All this allowed one of the authors to consider the problem of deuteron-deuteron interaction in other respects and to predict the cold fusion [7, 11].

Quantum object is getting classical one with a simultaneous increasing of its mass, i.e. in the case of superposition of a large number of wave packets. The case when all of packets consisting a body will consolidate and spread simultaneously is impossible in physics, as they have different velocities and masses. That is why such a combination seems as a stable and permanent object, moving according to the classical mechanics laws, though every packet is described in terms of the Quantum Mechanics. It looks like all particles in the Universe owe their existence to each other, and the **Universe itself is just a mathematical illusion, a trick.**

In justice to the adherents of the Complementary we have to say the following. They do not retract it, though they have to wriggle, they have to tell that particles always go to the mirror as correlated pairs, and one of them goes through, but the second is reflected. Of course we need to consider the induced radiation effect, when the one atom's radiation is increasing the probability of emitting from another excited atom of the same source, but it does not always happen. Let us return to the principle of Complementary. It is clear, that if we would not be interested in the nature of the particle and consider it just as an indivisible point then the principle of Complementary is correct. It is a very curious principle and it is amazing how N. Bohr could invent it.

In recent years a numerous of experiments was carried out, which found out superluminal speeds. Not debating if the special theory of relativity is right or not, let us show that in the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory (UUQT) any velocity is possible and the velocity of light is not maximum possible.

Let us consider Euclidean plain space, in which the photon propagates along the X -axis. According to the UUQT it is a wave packet and it could be presented as an infinite sum of harmonic components, that exist on the X -axis, figuratively speaking, placed at a distance of a million light years ahead and backwards. Now if we place on the X -axis arbitrarily far some special device, creating an anomalistic high dispersion, then the photon could occur at the exit of the device, because the harmonic components shifted each other. The most interesting in this process is that

nothing has moved between incident and reconstructed photons at this velocity! With other

words, the **conventional definition of the velocity is getting obsolete** [19, 23].

Figure 5. Experiments of L. Wang - superluminal light propagation.

Such experiments were carried out by several teams (in Berkeley, Vienna, Cologne, Florence, etc.) and they emerged the superluminal speeds. The most interesting were Lijun Wang's investigations [27] in which the velocity 310 times higher than the speed of the light (Fig. 5) was found. Wang gives the same interpretation as ours, but only for an impulse of light. In this case it is a wrong interpretation, because in the experiment the envelope of the light pulse is not distorted absolutely, but it has to be obligatory, and Wang notices that it is amazed. He supposes that the special theory of relativity is absolutely destroyed. But it is not quite true.

Our idea that particles are wave packets is an absolutely original idea for the world wide science. The waves at the Fig. 5 have to be realized as separated partial waves of the spectral decomposition of the wave packets of the separated photons, but not as a spectral decomposition of the light pulse. Then the form of the momentum envelope will not be distorted.

The aspects of the Unitary Quantum Theory are confirmed by results of their practical applications to traditional tasks of physics. **The UUQT allows firstly in the international science, not either to compute the electron charge and the fine structure constant (1/137) with the great precision (0.3%)**

[9-10] but even to compute masses of many elementary particles [15, 16, 18] (with the accuracy of 0.1-0.003%)! It is amazing that in the calculated spectrum of masses there is a particle mass about 131.7 GeV (L=2,m=2) that could be called Higgs boson [24].

The Modern Standard Model and quantum theories of field couldn't even raise these problems mathematically. It should be stressed that when we will find the spectrum of masses and charge of electron, time won't be a part of the ultimate equations and it will stay Newtonian. *In the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory all interactions and particle production (packet split) are considered as an effect of diffraction of the packets by each other because of the nonlinearity.* An analytical solution of these tasks will require new mathematical methods, and it is not even clear how to start with it at presence.

Approximated equation with the oscillating charge

There are strong hard rules in the modern theoretical physics. Any new theory has to include classical results. This is strictly satisfied because the Hamilton-Jacobi relativistic equation and Dirac equation follow from the UUQT, i.e. all modern basics of the fundamental quantum science. In the

linear equations of the UUQT the mass was replaced by the rest energy divided to square speed of light, and then the system of 32 nonlinear integro-differential equations appears as a consequence. They were firstly found out by L. Sapogin and V. Boichenko [8] in 1984, and only in 1988 they solved the dimensionless scalar version of this equation that allows to get the fine structure constant $1/137$ and electron charge with accuracy 0.3% [9,10].

In this approximation of the UUQT, the wave packet is realized as a spatial divided electric charge that oscillates, its equation depends on time, coordinate and velocity and it could work in the rough model of the particle as oscillated charge, so we can exploit the Newton equations. It is becoming easy to see the tunneling effect: while the moving particle is approaching to the potential barrier, in the phase when the charge is extremely small, it is easy for it to go through the barrier, and when the quantity of the charge is large, the repulsion force is increasing, and the particle will be reflected. The numerical solution of these equations [14-16, 20], for the most common quantum tasks emerges approximately the same results as the calculation of the general Quantum Mechanics (QM). By the way, by means of the UUQT it is possible to get this equation from the Schrodinger's one with very low energies [14,15]. But there are though some interesting differences. The equations of motion of the oscillated charge were not treated in physics before and they have an important difference from the classical laws of motion - the invariance of the motion in the relation to invariance translations. **It means the absence of the great classical momentum and energy conservation laws.** They appear in the UUQT and then in the classical mechanics only with an averaging for all particles.

Now we obtain Uncertainty relations [13-15, 19, 23]. As far as the particle (wave packet) is periodically appearing and vanishing at de Broglie wave length (more precisely, the packet disappears twice, and the probability of its detecting is sufficiently big in maximum region only) the position of such a packet may be detected with error

$$\Delta x \geq \frac{\lambda}{2} \quad \text{and then} \quad \Delta x \cdot P \geq \frac{h}{2}$$

As at measuring of momentum module is inevitable the error $P = 2P$, then we have following inequality: $\Delta x \cdot \Delta P \geq h$. The statements of standard quantum mechanics that particles do not have a trajectory become more understandable. Of course, there is a lot of truth in those words. First, it is possible to say so about intermittent (dotted) motion of the particle with oscillating charge. Second, any packet (particle) is able during its motion to split into

few parts. Each of those parts being summed with vacuum fluctuation may product, in principle, some new particles. Or *visa versa* the broken particle may vanish at all and contribute to general fluctuating chaos of the vacuum. But in any case it is better to have more clear idea of particle concrete motion than operate with generally accepted nowadays-obscure sentence about lack of trajectory.

The consideration of the problems concerning oscillations of particles with an oscillating charge in a parabolic well (harmonic oscillator) besides the common results of QM for stationary states results in two different solutions that are shown on Fig. 6. New amazing solutions appeared, one of them was called "Maternity home" and another was called "Crematorium". In the first case the energy of the particle can increase indefinitely, furthermore if we proceed from a very low initial quantity in the equation, it results in the increasing of the energy of the particle in the production of the matter, indeed. The second solution could due to collapse (disappear) of the matter-particle. These solutions are logically independent directly, and their appearance depends on initial phase. With other words, one solution describes the matter (energy) production, and another one its collapse; and it may be said that the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory (UUQT) allows to describe the creation of the matter and the Universe, but not as a result of the Big Bang. The Universe wouldn't be given to us in the static form, it arose in some way and it continues to develop, and we could see that one of the basic features is the filling of space by matter.

New sources of energy.

As well known, in all experiments the local law of energy conservation (LEC) and the law of conservation of momentum in individual quantum processes are correct only for high-energy states. For low energies we can't claim that, because of the uncertainty relation and the stochastic nature of QM's predictions. That is why the idea of the global, but not of local LEC exists invisibly in the QM and it is not a new one.

For the physics it only means that for the stationary solution with fixed discrete energy levels (the general QM) of the velocity of the particle reflected by a wall is equal to incident one. The UUQT allows to consider another ways too. Thus if the velocity of the particle for every reflection is decreasing, then it is corresponding to the "Crematorium" solution, but if it is increasing, then it is corresponding to the "Maternity home". What scenario would turn to the reality depends on the initial phase of the wave function and on the energy of the particle. Besides the UUQT is fundamentally inapplicable for closed systems, because such systems are idealizations,

which are very useful, but not according to the base of consideration used in the UUQT.

Anyway, the whole modern science, including the Quantum Mechanics (QM), is still based on the great LEC. However, there is a difficult situation in the Quantum Mechanics. It deals with the fact that the LEC follows only from the Newton mechanics. QM generalizes the facts of the classical mechanics including all of its laws, but its results have a sufficiently statistical nature, they are correct only for large amounts of particles. But how do we have to consider single particles, with their individual processes? It appears that for the single particles LEC does not follow from QM (!), thus individual events are absolutely incidental and do not follow this law. ***To evade this question it was announced that Quantum Mechanics does not describe individual events (!?)***

Let us discuss a thought experiment. To make our reasons more simple let operate a certain quantum ball-particle. If the ball is approaching to the wall, then its velocity after reflection will always be equal to the incident velocity (here we neglect a quantity of the friction force and consider that the ball and the wall are perfectly elastic). In the case of the quantum ball the velocity after the reflection would possess the whole arrange of the values, in different experiments under equal conditions. There would be some balls that would be reflected with velocities that are higher and some that are lower than the initial velocity, and some of them with velocities equal to the incident one, and every case would be considered statistically in the terms of the Quantum Mechanics.

Let us answer the following question: what would happen if we place another wall opposite the first, and would try to increase the velocity of the ball after every reflection? Then we would get increasing of energy of the ball without action of any external force. The energetic of the systems in the XXI century will treat the question of constructing of initial conditions for a numerous quantity of particles to realize only the "Maternity home" solution so that the "Crematorium" solution would be damped as far as possible. But it depends on the selection of initial phases and the geometry of the system.

Thus, if we use the ideas of the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory appropriately then does not exist a general prohibition for creating of a quantum perpetuum mobile. Formally there is no such a prohibition even in the general Quantum Mechanics, because there are no conservation laws for a single process under the low energy conditions, but it treats with probabilities instead of this. In other words, the Quantum Mechanics (QM) also offers

opportunities for getting energy by collecting of random process somehow. It seems that UUQT affords today such an opportunity and suggests the ways how to regulate the values of probabilities.

Together with theoretical investigations plentiful of numerical solutions of equations with oscillating charge were performed, momentum of particles falling with different velocities were summarized and the result was compared to momentum of reflected particles. It was found out that for different repulsive potentials, the total momentum of reflected particles is equal to momentum of the falling particles with a high accuracy, but for a single scattering particle the value of momentum could be either less or more than the momentum of the falling particle. This problem is very complicated and it requires subsequent researches as all this depends on initial conditions (velocity, phase, distance) complexly as well.

The prospects following from the UUQT are not even the most significant. Any flat bans as the impossibility of perpetuum mobile creation and any other confirmations of the immovability of conservation laws are unacceptable in philosophy. No, these laws would never be neglected; but there would be such areas in science and technology, very limited in the beginning, so that these laws would be not enough.

The problem of existing of the global conservation laws (we have proved that they are not local laws) is left in abeyance. Nothing but the idleness and atavism of the human thinking lead to it. But this idleness of thinking --concerning the physics-- manifests itself in the intuitive atavism for the Newton laws.

Yes, the conservation laws are incontestable in the classical mechanics and in terms of this theory a continuously operating machine is theoretically impossible. It should be stressed that the conservation laws were transferred to the Quantum Mechanics as an object of worship of the classical mechanics. But the Quantum Mechanics is more fundamental, Newton laws follow from it as a particular case. **And if in the terms of the Unitary Quantum Mechanics a possibility to get energy from nothing is theoretically possible, thus a quantum perpetuum mobile could be constructed.**

It is made possible by means of the equation with oscillating charge. It describes single particles; the difference in their behavior depends on the initial phase of the wave function, but there are no conservation laws for an individual particle at all, they appear only after an ensemble averaging. The equation with an oscillating charge is absolutely new

type of motion equation [11-17]. For such equation energy and impulse conversation laws do not exist. It appears after the ensemble averaging. By the way Schrodinger mechanics also do not propose energy conversation laws for small energies (it can offer only a probability of this or that event happening) but it cannot advise how to combine processes and energy liberation while UQT can. A theorem on the circulation does not work in the equation with oscillating charge that allows to use different way to move charge from the point *A* to the point *B*, but different ways operations will be diverse and this difference should be used.

The authors are trying to design new power plant working at these principles. We think that such a plant will be able to produce energy with extremely small spending of energy. If such power program would be fulfilled on our Planet then it will no doubt result in overheating of the environment. But UQT suggests the solution again: we can construct refrigerating plants which realize the “Crematorium” solution and promote the cooling. Extra heat will disappear. Numerous experiments with the cold nuclear fusion (including the latest of Andrea Rossi - Italy) have shown that nuclear reactions do exist but the nuclear reactions products by themselves are not enough for the explanation of huge amount of heat being produced. It is the responsibility of the UQT solutions “Maternity home” [13-15, 19, 20, 23]. So it looks like catalysis mechanism described [13-15, 22]. Besides all the equation with oscillating charge is quite good in describing the wave properties of the particle. We predict that experiments on the diffraction reflection of electrons from the lattice (classical experiments of Davisson Germer) can be simulated by supercomputer, but authors do not have such possibility.

Interestingly enough, there are devices called Testatik Machine M/L Converter from religious group Methernitha. They belong to a religious Christian commune, situated in Linden near Bern. Their maker is Swiss physicist Paul Baumann living in the commune. These fantastic devices run as direct current generators, are made as a four dimensions (sizes) type with power value of 0.1, 0.3, 3 and 10 kW. In outward appearance this device resembles an electrostatic machine with Leyden jars, so familiar from school physics laboratory. There are two acrylic discs with 36 narrow sectors of thin aluminium stuck to it. The discs rotate in different directions and their mechanical energy is hundreds times lower than produced energy it accounts for about 100 mW in measurements. The largest device with the power value of 10 kW has disc diameters more than 2 m, and the smallest has 20 cm; the device with the power value of 3 kW has 20 kg in weight. There is no cooling or heating of the air during the long operation of the device, it just smells of ozone there. It was found out that the inventor doesn’t clearly understand the principle of operation of the device.

Professor S. Marinov (Austria), whom the commune had given as a present the device with the power value of 100 W wrote in his book called “Difficult way to the truth --documents on the violation of conservation laws” , issued in 1989 by International Publishers East-West: “*I can confirm without any doubt that this device is a classical perpetuum mobile. Without any initial impact, it could rotate an unlimited long period of time and generate electrical energy equal to 100 W... In that device, the motor and generator are connected... However, it is not clear how it is possible*”. (back translation).

Figure 6.

The authors of the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory know approximately how this device is constructed, but in this article we are going to do only what is absolutely clear: we are going to show that the operation of this device completely corresponds with the UUQT. Evidently, it operates due to the charge

separation concept. Let us consider two metallic spherical surfaces with a hole isolated from the Earth and from each other. If we carry a first electron from sphere *A* to the inner surface of sphere *B* through the hole by means of an isolated stick, then there appears a potential difference. Further, if we carry the second

one and the subsequent electrons, sphere A would attract the carried charge, and B -would repeal it. It is

clear that to move the charge we will have to spend energy. (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Work for transferring the charge depends on the mode of transferring and on the path.

In the Technical University MADI (Moscow) professor V.I. Uchastkin gives lectures on the Unified Unitary Quantum Theory (UUQT) and new energy sources. In his explanations, he uses the figurative analogy: *Let us consider a sack of potatoes which mass is m. If we carried it to the fourth floor (the height is h), then we spend the quantity of work opposite to the gravitational field which is equal to mgh. And if we throw it down we would get kinetic energy $mv^2/2$, and these quantities would be equal to each other. But we could also carry not the whole sack, but every potato one by one. The work of one quantum of a potato s transfer depends on time, velocity and coordinate, and it must be carried in such way that the spent work would be minimal. If you carry the whole sack in this way, you can get the quantity $mv^2/2 > mgh$. So, there are no changes in the system, but the energy has appeared.*

Prospects

Let us remember the problem about the maintenance of long-term flights to the outer space with electricity. The Prof. Uchastkin’s analogy describes precisely a theoretical approach for solving this problem. Of course, there is a great deal to do though, to understand what phenomenon will play the role of those quantum potatoes and how to construct an instrument that would be able to support a minimal energy to bring them to the fourth floor. How can a spaceship be supplied with energy during many months of flight? Near the Earth, photovoltaic cells are used but the more the distance to the Sun is increasing, the more needless they are; using of a nuclear energy source is problematical for different causes.

Today we can neither improve this situation considerably nor do we have even any theoretical conditions which could let us approach it. On the base of such a situation there are common ideas of

the construction of matter and its properties. Now then, a new conception of physics is being proposed. Like many others as well. If we stay by the space technology, it s over constructing of engines based on new principles of energy production, maintaining of real-time telecommunication on the distances in outer space, free of limits which are proper to the diffusion of electromagnetic waves. It follows from the foregoing that UUQT opens up a perspective of a solution for the communication problem on extremely wide distances in outer space, excluding the limits of information exchange between Earth and spaceship. The theory also predicts the approaches to creating of the new energy sources and of the new types of engines that would be almost ideal for creating of spaceships of the future.

Conventional jet propulsions transform the conducted energy in the kinetic energy of the beam of a working body flowing from the engine, and the reaction force of this beam the pulling force accelerate the spaceship. Therefore space flights to extremely wide distances will require huge stocks of working body. A classical progression curve reflects the velocity increasing of a thrown-off mass of the working body. Though there is a possibility for creating of a very weak constant pulling but(!) without throwing off of mass.

Let us use the method of analogy again. Regard a classical trick problem in physics for universities admission tests: there is a boat in motionless water and a man with a sandbag in this boat. Can he move the boat by performing any manipulations with the sandbag, for an endless time?

Correct answer: throw the sandbag from the front part of the boat to its back, then carry it back slowly, throw it again and so on. As the viscous friction force by Stocks is proportional to the velocity, the boat will perform swinging motions, over which some linear

movement will be applied. Based on this idea, marsch buggies were constructed in Germany--there is heavy mass moving in there, in one direction quickly and back slowly. Many decades ago, the same effect (Dean`s engine) was wide-ragingly discussed in the USSR in popular science magazines and on TV.

There is a similar phenomenon in the classical electrodynamics as well as in the quantum electrodynamics and it s related to the Lorentz radiative friction force. The appearance of Lorentz force becomes evident by considering the interaction of the charge and the field caused by it. For a motionless charge the force of such an interaction or self-action is equal to zero, otherwise the free charge would experience a self-acceleration. The charge begins to move, but the electromagnetic field, as its spread velocity is finite, can`t reschedule immediately. The accelerated charge practically flies onto its own field; with other words, this effect can be described as appearance of energy flow which is directed upstream to the flow and slowing it down. It generates electromagnetic viscosity which value is related to the acceleration.

How can this phenomenon be used? If there is a charge cloud in flat capacitor, it is possible to make it swing between sheets with different values of acceleration forwards and backwards by applying a sawing motion to the sheets. Because of different forces of radiation friction in the alternate and opposite direction, pulling force appears along the lines of electric field. The radiation of such accelerated charges is always perpendicular to their movement and can be screened, but the most important thing on it is the fact that it doesn`t change its impulse in relation to the direction of the capacitor`s field. It may be paradoxical, but it seems that we get a pulling force by spending energy for this process without throwing-off of any mass in the direction, which is opposite to the motion`s one. The authors even published in the US-magazine Journal of New Energy vol.5, #1, 2000 an article, containing an exact analytical solution of this problem: the pulling of some micrograms appears in a flat capacitor, containing a cloud of 10^{19} electrons in which the distance between the sheets is many meters long, by applying of sawing potential of millions of volts. Of course, it is an insignificant result in relation to such a huge (hypothetical) instrument employment, and the using of electron cloud in a flat capacitor has practically no prospects. But if stabile charged particles exist which mass is at least one billion of electron mass, then this idea becomes very interesting from the technical point of view. Do such stabile charged leptons exist at all and how is it possible to generate them in a sufficiently large number? Today nobody can give an answer...

To generate pulling it is still possible to throw off the mass/ matter, created potential hole, accelerating in it in the same moment. Generally, UUQT allows such solutions that are evident from the "Maternity home" solution.

Let us consider the results. UUQT will in future let us solve several basic problems of the worldwide energy supply and all problems in outer space: immediate information changing, the problem of energy supply and constructing of new engine types. It is absolutely precipitant to make technical plans for those solutions, but the foregoing should be considered not as a wanton imagination, but as a possible future program of fundamental researches to transpose our civilization to new physical principles.

The UQT ideas are presented in instinctively absolutely clear picture of quantum events in terms of figures and movements. And philosophical principal of Complementarity can be now retired with well-deserved honors. In spite of mathematical complexity, the UQT delivers the physics from ordinary Quantum Mechanics paradoxes and consequently frank words of Richard Feynman: "I can easily say that nobody understands quantum mechanics" will become the property of history.

Moreover, it became possible:

- 1) to obtain after solving some QUT equations an electron charge with the high precision;
- 2) to obtain after solving the scalar telegraph equation the mass spectrum of numerous elementary particles with appropriate precision the mass spectrums of numerous elementary particles[14-16, 18]. The same spectrum was followed from the solutions of the Schroedinger equation and Klein-Gordon integro-differential equations. The risk of computed mass spectrum being random is less than 10^{-60} . Of course such results cannot be obtained without sacrifice. What would be offered in sacrifice if Ordinary Quantum Mechanics is replaced by the Unitary Unified Quantum Field Theory (UUQFT):
 1. There are no in UUQFT strict principles of superposition. It is violated if wave packets are colliding.
 2. There are no strict close systems in UUQF and the Conservation Laws work for big energies only. Note that the Conservation Laws forbid beginnings of the Universe.
 3. The classical relativistic relation between energy and impulses is valid in UUQFT only after averaging of observed phenomena and Relativistic Invariance itself is not "the sacred cow".
 4. The Space in UUQFT is not homogenous and not isotropic.
 5. The particles and their interaction are not local.

6. The existing Standard Model Quantum Theory of Elementary Particles requires much alteration.
7. The velocity concept as quotient from division of the traversed path to sometime interval is not quite appropriate in UQT.

If a wave packet (particle) is spreading along the Metagalaxy and then appearing somewhere else, what should we do with the rate, if nothing moves between the points of disappearance and arrival, does it mean that particle has just simply disappeared and then appeared in a new place? There was observed resembling crushing defeat of physics 50 years ago as “weak interaction” burst, so to say, into physics. As soon UQT is nonlinear, it automatically combines all four interactions that can pass from one into another distance. Below we analyze the most important fields of science from UQFT general physics positions.

Lorentz transformations

It's quite complicated. The special relativity is in fact Lorentz transformations (1904) derived by V.Vogt (1887) in the century before last. These transformations followed from the properties of Maxwell equations which are also proposed in the nineteenth century (1873). One of these equations connecting electrostatic field divergence and electric charge (Gauss' law of flux), in fact is just another mathematical notation of Coulomb's law for point charges.

But today anybody knows that Coulomb's law is valid for fixed point charges only. It doesn't work for the frequently moving charges. Besides anybody knows that lasers beams are scattered in vacuum one over another, which is absolutely impossible in Maxwell equations. *That means that Maxwell equations are approximate* - and for the moving point charges experimental results essentially differs from the estimated ones in the case charges areas are overlapping.

Few people think about the shocking nonsense of presenting in any course of physics of point charge electric field in the form of a certain sun with field lines symmetrically coming from the point. But electric field is a vector, and what for is it directed? The total sum of such vectors is null, isn't it?

There are no attempts to talk about, but such idealization is not correct. We should note that Sir Isaak Newton did not use term of a point charge at all, but it's ridiculous to think that such simple idea had not come to him! As for Einstein, he considered “*electron is a stranger in electrodynamics*”. **Maxwell equations are not ultimate truth and so we should forget, disavow the common statement about**

relativist invariance requirement being obligatory permission for any future theory.

To reassure severe critics we should note that UQT is relativistic invariant, it allows to obtain correct correlation between an energy and impulse, mass increases with a rate, as for relativistic invariance just follow of the fact that the envelope of moving packet is quiet in any (including non-inertial) reference systems. To be honest we should note that subwaves the particles consist of are relativistic abnormal, at the same time envelope of our wave packet being immovable in all coordinate-systems corresponds to of Lorentz transformations.

The success of Maxwell equations in description of the prior-quantum view of world was very impressing. Its correlation of the classical mechanics in forms of requirement to correspond Lorentz transformations was perfectly confirmed by the experiments that all these had resulted in unreasoned statement of Maxwell equations being an ultimate truth.

Other reasons for this were later very carefully investigated by a disciple of one of the authors (L.S.), Professor Yu.L.Ratis. (S.Korolev Samara State Aero-Space University), who has formulated the modern spinor quantum electrodynamics from the UQT point of view:

1. Maxwell equations contain constant c , which is interpreted as phase velocity of a plane electromagnetic wave in the vacuum.
2. Michelson and Morley have never measured the dependence of the velocity of a plane electromagnetic wave in the vacuum on the reference system velocity as soon plane waves were mathematical abstraction and it was impossible to analyze their properties in the laboratory experiment in principle.
3. Electromagnetic waves cannot exist in vacuum by definition. A spatial domain where an electromagnetic wave is spreading is no longer a vacuum. Once electromagnetic field arises in some spatial region at the same moment, such domain acquires new characteristic, because it became a material media. And such media possesses special material attributes including power and impulse.
4. Since electromagnetic wave while coming through the abstract vacuum (the mathematical vacuum) transforms it in a material media (physical vacuum) it will interact with this media.
5. The result of the electromagnetic wave and physical vacuum interaction are compact wave packets, called photons.
6. The group velocity of the wave packet (photon) spreading in the media with the normal dispersion is always less its phase velocity.

All abovementioned allows making unambiguous conclusion: *the main difficulties of the modern relativistic quantum theory of the field arise from deeply fallacious presuppositions in its base. The reason for this tragic global error was a tripe substitution of ideas-velocity of electromagnetic wave packets 'c' being obtained in numerous experiments physics was adopted as constant 'c' appearing in Maxwell equations and Lorentz transformations. Such blind admiration of Maxwell and Einstein geniuses (authors in no case do not doubt in the genius of these persons) had led XX century physics up a blind alley. The way out was in the necessity of revision of the entire fundamental postulates underlying the modern physics.* Exactly that was done by UUQFT [13-15, 19, 23].

Some time ago CERN has conducted repeated experiments of the neutrino velocity measurement that appeared to be higher than velocity of the light. For UUQFT they were like a balm into the wounds. The administration of CERN renounced after sometimes these results considering them as the consequence of experimental errors. As far as the authors know, not all participants of this experiment agree to such renouncing. Besides, many astronomers detect superluminal velocities during observations of stars and galaxies [29]. In fact the movements in excess of the light velocity were discovered earlier by numerous groups of researches. Nearly everybody disbelieved it [29]. The importance of these experiments for UUQFT is settled in the article [23] where at the page 69 it is written that *this should be considered as direct experimental proof of UUQFT principle.*

Note, this question is terribly complicate and probably is to be leaved to next generations. From one side, the time in UQT exists, so to say, in our head only. From other side, the Lorentz Transformations describe correctly some experimental facts, for example, the mass growing with velocity. Otherwise, all atomic accelerators would be out of order. Thereafter, it is a big mistake to consider all Special Relativity Theory as erroneous.

Standard model

As soon relativistic invariance underlies every of the numerous quantum theories of the field, it leaves a devilish imprint at everything. Nevertheless relativistic ratio between energy and impulse although being absolutely correct in fact are not obligatory follow from relativistic invariance only and can result from another mathematical reasons that will be discovered in future. Nowadays Standard Model (SM) contains the most elegant mathematical miracles of researches which hands were tied with

relativistic strait-jacket and it not so bad describes these experimental data. Amazing that it was possible to think it out at all.

Nowadays to confirm SM one should find a Higgs boson and for this purpose the governments of some countries assigned essential sums for the construction of Large Hadrons Collider (LHC). For entire SM the interaction with Higgs field is extremely important, as soon without such a field other particles just will not have mass at all, and that till lead into the theory destruction.

To start with we should note that the Higgs field is material and can be identified with media (aether) as it was in former centuries. But SM authors as well as modern physics have carefully forgotten about it. We would not like to raise here once again the old discussion about it. It s a quite complicated problem and let us leaves it to the next generation.

But another problem of SM has never mentioned before: in the interaction with Higgs field any particle obtains mass. As for Higgs boson itself, it is totally falling out of this universal for every particle mechanism of mass generation! And that is not a mere trifle, such mismatching being fundamental fraught with certain consequences for SM.

After Higgs boson discovery nothing valuable for the world will happen except an immense banquet. Of course boson will justify the waste of tens billions of Euros But even now some opinions in CERN are expressed that probably boson non-disclosure will reveal a series of new breath-taking prospects and where were these voices before construction, we wonder? But that's not the point! If this elusive particle were the only weakness of SM!

To our regret today this theory cannot compute correctly the masses of elementary particles including the mass of Higgs boson. More worse, that SM contains from 20 to 60 adjusting arbitrary! - parameters (there are different versions of SM). SM does not have theoretically proved algorithm for spectrum mass computation and no ideas how to do it!

All these bear strong resemblance to the situation with Ptolemaic models of Solar system before appearance of Kepler's laws and Newton s mechanics. These earth-centered models of the planets movement in Solar system had required at first introduction of so called epicycles specially selected for the coordination of theoretical forecasts and observations. Its description of planets positions was quite good; but later to increase the forecasts accuracy it had required another bunch of additional

epicycles. Good mathematicians know that epicycles are in fact analogues of Fourier coefficients in moment decomposition in accordance with Kepler's laws; so by adding epicycles the accuracy of the Ptolemaic model can be increased too. However that does not mean that the Ptolemaic model is adequately describing the reality. Quite the contrary.

The Unitary Quantum Theory allowed computing the mass spectrum of elementary particles without any adjusting parameters. By the way computed spectrum [14-16, 18] has particle with mass 131.51711 GeV ($L=2$, $m=2$). Once desired it can be called Higgs boson, it lies within declared by the CERN+Tevatron mass interval 125-140 GeV expected to contain Higgs boson. CERN promises to obtain more precise mass value by December 2012.

Note the following remarkable fact: the standard theory allowed to detect spectra by using always the quantum equations with outer potential and as corollaries to geometric relations between de Broglie wave's length and characteristic dimension of potential function. The quantum equation of our theory does not contain the outer potential and describe a particle in empty free space; the mass quantization arises owing to the delicate balance of dispersion and non-linearity which provides the stability of some wave packets number. It is the first case when spectra are detected by using the quantum equations without outer potential.

Nuclear physics.

Nuclear physics as a part of quantum theory is very luckless. Thus the potential of the strong interactions is so complicated that no one even very bulky and intricate mathematical expression is able to describe with more or less veracity the experiments of two nucleons interaction. This interaction depends in very complicated manner from all parameters of the nucleons movement and their orientation towards vectors of velocity, acceleration, spin, magnetic movement, etc. Scarcely one can find a parameter which practice interaction does not depend on. From UQT point of view the strong interactions appear in the result of nucleons represented by the wave packets overlapping. Today the way of mathematical notation of the overlapping wave packets interaction is absolutely vague as soon nonlinear interaction in any space-time point of the waves is different due to different amplitudes.

It's a really complicated problem as soon there is only one nonlinear mathematical problem existing for each space-time point and even with the intuitive clearance of situation we do not expect its soon solution. The complete understanding of the nuclear structure hardly can be expected in the soonest time

without exact expression for the potential of the strong interaction.

In general it should be noted that quantum world looks more clear and simple in UQT than in the general quantum mechanics, but we cannot repeat it while speaking about the mathematics used. The appearance of the exact analytical solution of the scalar problem of elementary particles mass spectrum can be considered as Fate gift (or God's help) for UQT. By the way the standard Schrodinger quantum mechanics has the same gift -- the exact analytical solution of the Hydrogen atoms equation.

The nuclear process at small energies should be reviewed. Today the strict nuclear physics does not assume nuclear reactions at small energies and that contradict experimental data. Here we should also note our skepticism towards the idea of nuclear fusion in Tokamaks, we consider this way as hopeless. To justify these experiments we have to mention that the solution was obtained in the deficient of other ideas and under the great pressure of the future power problems. But the use of the reactions of classical cold fusion for the power output is also difficult due to the complexity of colliding nuclei phasing. This phenomenon is well described by the equation with oscillating charge, while the cold nuclear fusion had been predicted in UQT 6 years before its real discovery [7].

Solid-state physics.

The band theory of solid is based at the point on the solution of the problem of an electron movement in the field of two or more charges. But this problem does not have analytical solution yet, in practice a speculative quality solution is used only. The results are that electrons in the solid have quite specific allowed power bands. This field of the science is very successful and hardly will be revised. Any solution of the equations with the oscillating charge for the electron moving in the field of few nuclei also result in appearance of allowed and forbidden bands [14,15,21].

Somewhat apart is classical tunneling effect. In UQT the probability of tunneling effect appearance depends on the phase of the wave function (in contrast to the ordinary quantum theory, where at the squaring of the wave function module its dependence on the wave phase totally disappears). It could be interesting to prove such dependence by the experiments. It can be easily done if creating a new transistor on the basis of absolutely new principle of the electron current control [21].

We are not going to analyze the modern theory of superconductivity, but we are sure that the equation

with oscillating charge will deepen on both understanding of superconductivity as well as mysterious properties of quantum liquids.

Astrophysics and Cosmology

The authors regret not being in sympathy with the ideas of the Universe origin from one singular point. The most amazing in this theory is a detailed computation of events occurred in the fractions of the first second just after the Big Bang. Today when the fundamental physics is making only first shy steps towards the real understanding of the quantum processes we still do not have clear model of the particles, or understanding of a spin appearance, of a charge and magnetic moments.

According to UQT the processes of the multiple particle production at collision is a common result of the waves packets of big amplitudes diffraction in periodic structures one another, as for the multiple outgoing in different directions particles they correspond to the general diffraction maximums. But we do not assume the responsibility of the mechanism of the multiple particles production for the Universe appearance. To our opinion the complete understanding of the quantum world will arise only after solving of 32 nonlinear integro-differential equations of UQT [8,13-15]. To their regret the authors are not able to solve these equations.

And many cosmologists would like to use theories assuming existence Universe localities where the energy is coming into being and also other localities where the energy annihilates. For example, British astronomer Fred Hoyle has developed the theory of Universe where it takes the place the continuous creation of matter. He wrote: *“Different atoms constituting the matter do not exist at some given moment of time and then after instant they exist already. I must admit this idea may look as strange. But all our ideas about creation are strange. According to previous theories the whole quantity of matter in Universe was coming into being just as whole and all process of creation looks as super-gigantic instant explosion. As for me, such idea seems much stranger, than idea of continuous creation”*. (F.Hoyle, La nature de l Universe, 1952.)

The official astronomical science does not accept the ideas of F.Hoyle and of some other astronomers (H.Bondi, T.Gold, and P.Jordan) about continuous creation of matter in Universe because the Conservation Laws are considered as infallible. But from the viewpoint of our UQT these ideas are quite not strange.

Our real world continuum consists of an enormous quantity of particles moving with different velocities. Partial waves of the postulated vanishing particles create real vacuum fluctuations that change in a very random way. Certain particles randomly appear in such a system, owing to the harmonic component energy of other vanished particles. The number of such dependant particles changes, though; they suddenly appear and vanish forever, as the probability of their reappearance is negligibly small, and so we do expect that all particles are indebted to each other for their existence. Yet, if some particles are disappearing within an object, other particles are arising at the same moment in that object due to the contribution of those vanishing particles harmonic components and vice versa.

The simultaneous presence of all of the particles within one discrete macroscopic object is unreal. Some constituent particles vanish within the object while others appear. In general, a mass object is extant overall, but is not instantaneously substantive and merely a false image. It is clear that the number of particles according to such a theory is inconstant and all their ongoing processes are random, and their probability analysis will remain always on the agenda of future research.

In accordance with UQT there are another solutions for the quantum harmonic oscillator besides stationary, where the given tiny incipient fluctuation is growing, gaining power and finally becoming a particle. It is so called “Mathernity Home” solution. There are also other solutions where substance (power) is disappearing. Such solutions have been called “Crematorium”. *May be Metagalaxy is simply entangled in searching the balance, isn't it?*

All this allows expecting that space continuum in the centers of Galaxies produces different particles, electrons, protons, neutrons, which are the sources of light atoms. Later thanks to the gravitation light atoms are transformed into gas nebulas where under gravity compression the stars are lighting. It is quite possible that the current theory of Stars evolution is correct in general while describing (via Supernova) the production of other atoms apart Hydrogen and Carbon the planets consist of. We do not think nuclear process at small energies (which are possible in UQT, but impossible in standard quantum theory) will essentially modify evolutionary view of the Galaxies development.

It is interesting that the state with the minimum quantum values $L=0, m=0$ belongs to the very heavy neutral scalar particle (WIMP) with our name $Dzhan$ and mass about 69.6 TeV, which in principle should purely interact with the others [15,16,18]. With the

growth of the quantum numbers the mass of the particle is diminishing. So there should be a lot of Dzhon-particles due to the small quantum numbers. And probably their existence is responsible for the dark matter in general, in accordance with some evaluations Metagalaxy consist of up to 80-90% of the dark matter.

Gravitational theory

It seems Gravitational theory should follow from 32 nonlinear integro-differential equations of UQT and the authors are expecting that it can be done in future [8,13-15]. Nevertheless we will make now some conservative assertions. The current data regarding the Universe expansion can be interpreted as the change of the gravitational potential sign (gravity is replacing by repulsion) at great distances for the great masses. Probably the difference between absolute the values of electric charge of a proton and an electron, say in 15-20 signs, is responsible for his phenomena, but for us this idea is extremely unsympathetic.

Gravitational interaction remains an extraordinary mysterious appearance in UQT as actually it has a very high speed of interactions distribution and approximately is in times weaker than electromagnetic interactions. The origin of such an enormously big number remains the greatest riddle.

On the other hand if any particle is a package of partial waves of some uniform field, probably is possible a following curious phenomenon which was observed and described by us more than once earlier [13-15, 19, 23]. If to put a ditch with the substance having abnormal dispersion on a way of the wave package moving in flat Euclidean space, the package after ditches can appear even if it is situated at distance of many light years from a package as formally mathematically harmonious components exist on all infinite rectilinear coordinate of package movement as ahead of it, and behind. Thus the package can disappear in that place where it was, and to appear at huge distances ahead of a package, or behind. Thus the package didn't move at all between points of disappearance and new appearance, and the normal idea of speed in the unitary quantum theory loses its initial meaning.

Similar teleportation was observed of ten times. Probably, it is actually a long-range action, (couplage à longue distance) observed in gravitation. A curious though appears that the waves building a package, could be connected with gravitation and all particles consists of a gravitational field. *Then this field can be a stage or a scene where all other processes with final speeds of interaction transfer are played. It will allow connecting the quantum theory and the gravitation theory which while aren't connected yet*

today in the future. But it is a task for the future generations.

At the same time according to the processed information (Hlistunov at all [28]) from Russian Command-and-Measuring Complex for the monitoring and control of the space objects at the entire moment of collision geodesic satellites Tope-Poseidon and GEO_IK began swaying at their orbits. Normally the orbit of a geodesic satellite lies inside the tube with about 1 km diameter and the orbit can be control with the high accuracy not more than one meter precision for the position data and centimeters per second for velocity.

During the collision the sensors registered 5-8 times increase of the trajectory tube diameter. In the same article Hlistunov [28] at all on the basis of correlation analysis of the position data measurements and information obtained from earthquake-detection station it was shown that the waves of gravitational potential variation were the trigger for earthquakes. To the authors regret they do not have the similar information from NASA.

Chemical catalysis

The process of chemical catalysis and the catalysts are the great mystery of the modern science. The number of chemical catalysis theories equals the number of chemical catalytic processes. A specialist in chemical catalysis used to think that this or that reaction is not going because of the needed catalyst has not been found. Even Michael Faraday studied these problems. He seems to say about platinum as being the universal catalyst. Only this (while platinum practically does not react with anything) immediately suggests an idea that chemical processes are not enabled at all and we should look for the physical universal mechanism of reactions.

The UQT has such a process. The details are listed in the articles [13-16, 20, 22-25]. The universal mechanism of heterogeneous catalysis, for example in Ammonia Synthesis, consists of the following: Nitrogen molecule falls into a cavity (hole a few tens of Angstroms unit size), then at some initial moment the molecule starts oscillating with an energy augmentation implementing solution of Maternity home like in a normal potential well - Fig.6. If the augmented energy excesses the binding energy of molecule Nitrogen then atomic Nitrogen at the exit from the cavity will be caught by protons (Hydrogen), form Ammonia and then quit the game and free cavity for the new deeds.

We are sure that in such a way water can be decomposed for Oxygen and Hydrogen. At normal

conditions the mixture of Oxygen and Hydrogen is stable. In other words two stable substances (water and gas mixture) are simply divided by a high energy barrier, that can be overcome (tunneling effect analogue) by using the exact catalyst and the UQT ideas. For today a lot of experiments of water decompositions are known, the energy evolved in the process of hydrogen combustion is ten times higher than necessary for decomposition. It makes possible to construct a water-engine for autos.

Conclusion

In essence, our theory discovered new world properties and new theoretical possibility of the radical transformation of the civilization.

Let us to remind of the prophetic words of the famous US science-fiction author Arthur Clarke: *Something that is theoretically possible will be achieved practically independent of technical difficulties. It's enough to desire it.* (back translation)- Profiles of the Future, 1963.

We would like to add the amazing phrase of A. de Saint-Exupéry: *"The truth is not something that could be proved, but something that makes all things easy and clear"* (back translation).

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